

A Artifact Appendix

A.1 Abstract

This artifact provides a Docker image containing all required binaries and instructions for conducting the two experiments presented in the paper. The SPEC benchmarks are not included due to license restrictions, however, they can be integrated into the artifact separately. Additionally, the artifact contains the source code, scripts, as well as the data and graphs from the presented experiments. As the transformation was applied manually in the evaluation, the scripts apply patches to the benchmarks to add the transformations.

A.2 Artifact check-list (meta-information)

- **Algorithm:** An analysis to detect region-based data-layout transformation statically.
- **Program:** SPEC CPU 2000 1.2, 2006 1.2, 2017 1.1.0 benchmarks. Not included due to its license.
- **Compilation:** Includes LLVM 16.0.0.
- **Run-time environment:** Tested on Ubuntu 22.04.3 (Kernel 6.2.0-39) with Docker 24.0.5. Includes the PAPI library 7.0.1 and Google Benchmark framework 1.8.2. The PAPI library requires root access to collect event counters.
- **Hardware:** Tested on a Intel x86-64 CPU. Root access is required to lock CPU frequency and to enable the PAPI library.
- **Metrics:** Execution time, Linux event counters (L1 and L2 cache misses).
- **Output:** Execution logs, graphs, and tables. Results obtained for the paper evaluation are included.
- **Experiments:** Data Reuse Impact (Section 5.3) and Transformation Evaluation (Section 5.4).
- **How much disk space required (approximately)?:** 1.6 GB for the docker image, 70 GB for the results generated during execution, and 7 GB for SPEC CPU benchmark suites.
- **How much time is needed to complete experiments (approximately)?:** 2-3 days, highly dependent on the CPU and locked frequency.
- **Publicly available?:** Yes.
- **Code licenses?:** Apache License v2.0 with LLVM Exceptions.
- **Archived?:** [10.5281/zenodo.10457086](https://zenodo.org/record/10457086)

A.3 Description

A.3.1 How delivered The artifact can be found archived in Zenodo: [10.5281/zenodo.10457086](https://zenodo.org/record/10457086) [19].

A.3.2 Hardware dependencies A CPU with access to hardware counters for cycles, cache misses, and instructions executed.

A.3.3 Software dependencies A working Docker installation and the SPEC CPU 2000, 2006, and 2017 benchmark suites.

A.4 Installation

A.4.1 Host Setup. To obtain more consistent and reliable results, lock the CPU frequency. For the experiments presented in this paper, the CPU was locked at (2.6 GHz). Try to use the CPU base frequency, which varies across CPUs.

```
$ sudo cpupower frequency-set --governor performance
$ sudo cpupower frequency-set -u 2.6GHz -d 2.6GHz
```

To enable the PAPI library, allow unprivileged users to see event counters.

```
$ sudo sh -c \
    'echo 1 > /proc/sys/kernel/perf_event_paranoid'
```

A.4.2 Docker Container. Download the Docker image, navigate to the directory containing the download to load the image, and then create and start a container. The `--privileged` flag is needed to use the PAPI library to instrument the experiments. The `-v` flag mounts a volume from the host to the container to make the SPEC benchmark suites available in the container, this flag is detailed in the next section.

```
$ docker load --input docker-artifact.tar.gz
$ docker create --privileged -it \
    --name artifact \
    -v host/spec/path:/home/artifact/spec \
    rebasedl-artifact
$ docker start artifact
```

A.4.3 SPEC 2000 Pre-Installation. To run the SPEC installation in the next section, installing Linux headers with the version that matches your system in the container is required. This requirement is specific to the SPEC 2000 installation and can be done with the following commands:

```
$ docker exec -u 0 -it artifact bash # root user
$ apt update && apt install -y linux-headers-$(uname -r)
$ exit
```

The matching Linux header may not be found if the host is not running Ubuntu 22.04. For an older version of the kernel, a possible solution is to change the Ubuntu repositories to a previous version. This can be done inside the container (as root user) with the following command, then, retry the header installation.

```
$ sed -i s/jammy/focal/g /etc/apt/sources.list
```

A.4.4 SPEC Setup. The SPEC CPU benchmark 2000, 2006, and 2017 suites must be installed in the folders `~/spec2000-install`, `~/spec2006-install`, and `~/spec2017-install` in the container.

To do so, first, make the SPEC suites available in the container: (i) create a folder that contains the already extracted SPEC CPU suites before the SPEC installation step in the host, (ii) substitute `host/spec/path` in the `docker create` command for the path to the created folder. This folder will be available inside the container in the path `~/spec`.

Then, install SPEC in the previously mentioned folders. The installation can be done manually, but the artifact provides the script `~/scripts/setup-spec.sh` to help with this step. For SPEC 2000 and 2006, this script patches a few benchmarks to avoid compilation failure. Additionally, this script fixes the installation step of SPEC 2000, which fails because it is an older suite. Note that if the SPEC suite versions differ from the ones mentioned in Section A.2, this script may fail.

Check if the paths defined at the beginning of this script correctly match the paths in the mounted volume (`~/spec`). This can be done, for example, with `vim` or `nano`. Then, run the installation script:

```
$ docker exec -it artifact bash
$ vim ~/scripts/setup-spec.sh # Check SPEC paths
$ ~/scripts/setup-spec.sh
$ exit
```

A.5 Experiment Workflow

A.5.1 Running the Analysis To run the RebaseDL analysis in all SPEC benchmarks and save the output logs, execute the following commands in the container:

```
$ mkdir ~/analysis
$ cd ~/scripts
$ ./build-all-benchmarks.sh 2000 ~/analysis && \
  ./build-all-benchmarks.sh 2006 ~/analysis && \
  ./build-all-benchmarks.sh 2017 ~/analysis
```

To inspect the candidates identified by the analysis by running, search the output logs with:

```
$ cd ~/analysis
$ grep -rn "Candidate"
```

Summarize the number of candidates found per benchmark by running:

```
$ cd ~/analysis
$ grep -r "Candidate" | uniq -c | cut -d':' -f1 | sort -h
```

A.5.2 Replicate Experiments. This workflow produces the results shown in the evaluation (Section 5) and it generates some additional graphs with results that were not shown due to space constraints. With the Docker container already started, run the container interactively using the following command.

```
$ docker exec -it artifact bash
```

To exactly replicate the methods used to obtain the results in this paper, run the following in the container:

```
$ mkdir ~/replica
$ ~/scripts/experiments/auto-eval.sh ~/replica
```

Finally, in the host, retrieve the results by running:

```
$ ID="$(docker ps -aqf 'name=^artifact$')"
$ docker cp ${ID}:/home/artifact/replica/ .
```

A.5.3 Script Details SPEC benchmarks can be run separately from the complete experiment workflow. The following commands show an example of how to build and run the 179.art benchmark.

```
$ # prints RebaseDL analysis output
$ ~/scripts/spec-benchmark.sh build 2000 179.art
$ # executes benchmark
$ ~/scripts/spec-benchmark.sh run 2000 179.art
```

The PAPI library calls and the RebaseDL transformation are applied to benchmarks through patches. The following commands exemplify how to modify the 179.art benchmark. After patching a benchmark, it must be built again.

```
$ cd ~/scripts/experiments/transformation-evaluation
$ # base: add PAPI lib calls to benchmark
$ ./patch-benchmark.sh base 2000 179.art
$ # opt: base + add RebaseDL transformation to benchmark
$ ./patch-benchmark.sh opt 2000 179.art
$ # reset: restore benchmark to original state
$ ./patch-benchmark.sh reset 2000 179.art
```

A.6 Evaluation and expected result

If using a similar environment, the result trends should follow what was presented in this paper. However, a different CPU may have different features, affecting the results. For example, changes to the cache sizes may affect the final results.

A.7 Experiment customization

All scripts accept the flag `-h` that shows a help message on how to use the script and the optional parameters that it accepts. Additionally, the script folders contain `readme.md` files with more information.

For the workflow that replicates the experiments (Section A.5.2), the script `auto-eval.sh` accepts additional parameters that allow changing the number of executions of the SPEC benchmarks and the input size for the Transformation Evaluation (Section 5.4).

The configuration files for SPEC can be found in the folder `~/scripts/spec-configs`. Inside this folder, the configuration files are the following. Modifying these files affects all scripts that compile SPEC benchmarks. Note that for SPEC 2000, the file is a template that scripts use as a base for the actual configuration file.

- `./spec2000/cpu2000-llvm-linux-x86.cfg.template`
- `./spec2006/cpu2006-llvm-linux-x86.cfg`
- `./spec2017/cpu2017-llvm-linux-x86.cfg`

A.8 Notes

- Depending on the host's configuration, `sudo` privileges may be required to run Docker.
- The graphs generated for the Transformation evaluation will fail if not all expected benchmarks are run, however, the summary tables are more flexible and can generate their outputs in this case.
- When tested, the artifact could not run in the Windows Subsystem for Linux because the PAPI library calls failed.
- The flag `-march=native` was present in all benchmarks of the evaluation, but it is disabled in the artifact for 502.gcc_r because it can make the execution of this benchmark fail.